

Table 1 Measurements of the external and postcranial characters. Measurements for *Calomyscus elburzensis*, *Meriones persicus*, *Rattus norvegicus*, *Rhombomys opimus*, and *Scarturus elater* were taken during this study, while those of *Apodemus witherbyi* (except the body weight and length of whiskers) were extracted from Kuncová & Frynta (2009). Number of the examined rodents for each species are written in parentheses. Mean and standard error are shown for *C. elburzensis* and *A. witherbyi*. Measurements are shown in Figure 14. Ratio of length to width are also calculated for sacrum, last lumbar vertebra, scapula, humerus, ulna, innominate bone, femur, and tibia.

Measured character	Abbreviation	Value (g or mm)						
		<i>Calomyscus elburzensis</i> (24)	<i>Apodemus witherbyi</i> (49)	<i>Meriones persicus</i> (1)	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i> (1)	<i>Rhombomys opimus</i> (1)	<i>Scarturus elater</i> (1)	
External	Body weight	BW	19.7± 0.1	20± 0.1	99	194	170	39
	Length of head and body	LHB	76.5± 0.2	98.2± 5.6	123	142	130	98
	Length of tail	LTA	84.5± 0.2	101.6± 7.2	124	157	129	151
	Total length of body	LB	162± 0.1	200± 0.2	247	299	259	249
	Length of hind foot	LHF	21.2± 0.1	21.5± 0.9	36	32	35	45
	Length of ear	LE	16.5± 0.1	16.2± 0.9	21	22	13	30
	Length of whiskers	LW	39± 0.4	27± 0.5	41	21	-	62
Skeletal Backbone	Length of sacrum	SL	9.1± 0.1	-	21.1	30.2	25.1	11.8
	Width of sacrum	WS	4.7± 0.1	4.7± 0.3	12.5	13	12	7.5
	Length of last lumbar vertebra	LLV	2.5± 0.04	3.1± 0.2	9.7	8.7	7.5	5.1
	Width of last lumbar vertebra (on transverse processes)	WLV	2.8± 0.07	5.4± 0.3	6.1	6.3	6	4.7
		SL/WS	1.93	-	1.68	2.32	2.09	1.57
		LLV/WLV	0.89	0.57	1.59	1.38	1.25	1.08

Scapula	Length of scapula	LS	9.3± 0.1	10.9± 0.6	20	22	20	-
	Width of scapula	WS1	5.7± 0.08	7.6± 0.4	11	13	17.5	-
	Width of scapula (distance between medial and inferior angles)	WS2	5.8± 0.1	8.3± 0.4	12.5	13.8	18.8	-
		LS/WS1	1.63	1.43	1.81	1.69	1.14	-
Forelimb	Length of humerus	LH	11.2± 0.1	13.6± 0.6	20	27.5	25	11.2
	Length of proximal part of humerus (= deltoid length of humerus)	LPH	5.2± 0.1	5.8± 0.3	12.2	15.3	12.5	5.2
	Width of proximal part of humerus (including deltoid process)	WPH	1.8± 0.02	2.4± 0.1	4.2	5	5.3	2.2
	Humerus mediolateral diameter	HMLD	0.8± 0.01	-	2.1	2.3	2.5	1.2
	Width of distal part of humerus	WDH	1.4± 0.01	0.9± 0.06	3	4.9	4.8	2.5
	Width across the epicondyles (distance between lateral and medial epicondyles)	WE	2.8± 0.04	3.07± 0.1	5.5	7.5	7	3.6
	Length of ulna	LU	14± 0.1	15.8± 0.5	28	31	25	-
	Length of olecranon (to semi- lunar notch)	LO	1.5± 0.03	1.9± 0.1	3	4.2	4	-

	Width of proximal part of ulna and radius	WPU (WPU1+WPU2)	1.5± 0.02	1.7± 0.1	4	4.6	4.8	-
	Ulna mediolateral diameter	UMLD	0.7± 0.02	-	1.4	2.5	3	-
	Length of radius	LR	12± 0.1	-	22.7	23.7	18.7	13.2
	Length of third metacarpal bone	MC	3.3± 0.01	-	-	-	-	1.5
	Length of the proximal phalanx of third digit of manus	PPH	2.2± 0.01	-	-	-	-	1.1
		LH/HMLD	14	-	9.52	11.95	10	0.93
		LU/UMLD	20	-	20	12.4	8.33	-
	Length of ilium (including acetabulum)	LI	11.3± 0.08	19.3± 1.06	25	28.5	31.2	7.3
	Length of pubis symphysis	LPS	0.8± 0.02	-	7.4	4.3	7.5	1.1
	Length of ischiopubis	LIP	5± 0.03	5.9± 0.4	12.5	13.5	16	4.8
Innominate bone	Width of ischiopubis	WIP	6.1± 0.1	7.2± 0.5	13.8	16	17	6
	Width of ilium	WI	1.4± 0.05	1.2± 0.1	3	3.8	4.8	1.3
	Length of obturator foramen	LOF	5.2± 0.1	6.09± 0.4	11	12	12.5	2.5
	Width of obturator foramen	WOF	2.8± 0.03	2.6± 0.1	6	5.1	5	1.8
		(LI+LIP)/WIP	2.67	3.5	2.71	2.62	2.77	2.01
Hindlimb	Length of femur	LF	14.5± 0.1	18.5± 0.9	40	38.7	42.5	14.9

Width of proximal part of femur (including third trochanter)	WPF	1.8± 0.03	2.3± 0.2	5	6.1	7.4	-
Femur anteroposterior diameter	FAPD	0.9± 0.02	-	3	3.9	4.8	1.2
Width of distal part of femur	WDF	1.3± 0.02	1.5± 0.1	4.2	5	5.7	-
Femoral epicondylar breadth	FEB	2.6± 0.02	-	5	6.2	7	-
Width of femoral neck	WFN	0.9± 0.01	1.09± 0.09	2.5	2.8	3.2	1.1
Distance between greater trochanter of femur and femoral head	WTH	0.8± 0.02	0.8± 0.1	2.5	2.4	2.6	-
Height of greater trochanter	FGT	1.26± 0.2	-	4.6	4	6	1.2
Length of tibia	LT	18.9± 0.1	21.7± 0.8	37.5	40	-	21
Length of proximal part of tibia (to fusion of tibia and fibula)	LPT	9.3± 0.08	13.2± 0.5	21	26.2	23.5	7.5
Length of distal part of tibia (from fusion of tibia and fibula)	LDT	9.6± 0.08	8.5± 0.4	16.5	13.7	-	12.6
Width of proximal part of tibia (on tibial crest)	WPT	1.1± 0.02	1.6± 0.1	3.8	4.5	3	1.7

Tibia mediolateral diameter	TMLD	1.24± 0.05	-	2.4	2.6	-	1.2
Length of fibula	LFI	18.1± 0.1	-	36.2	41.3	-	20.1
Width of distal part of tibia and fibula	WDTF	0.8± 0.01	0.9± 0.08	2	2.5	-	1.1
Total length of calcaneus	CTL	4.68	-	9.8	8.75	8.82	-
Total width of calcaneus	CTW	2.35	-	3.75	5.62	4.71	-
Width of calcaneus neck	NW	0.93	-	1.81	1.87	1.97	-
Width of calcaneal tuberosity	TWC	1.25	-	1.87	2.73	2.50	-
Height of cuboid articular surface	CCH	1.03	-	2.25	3.75	3.47	-
Width of cuboid articular surface	CCW	0.82	-	1.87	2.5	3.12	-
Total length of astragalus	ATL	2.02	-	3.80	4.87	4.40	-
Total width of astragalus	ATW	1.72	-	3.75	4.87	4.47	-
Width of astragalus body	ABW	1.35	-	3.31	4.07	4.11	-
Width of astragalus head	HW	0.93	-	2.25	2.63	2.98	-
Lateral trochlear length	LTL	1.41	-	2.28	3.35	2.98	-
Medial trochlear length	MTL	1.09	-	1.52	2.25	2.23	-
Length of third metatarsal bone	LMT	9.8± 0.06	8.9± 0.3	15.5	15	13	13.7

Length of third
digit of pes

LTPH	6.8± 0.06	-	-	-	-	7.5
LF/FAPD	16.11	-	13.33	9.92	8.85	12.41
LT/TMLD	15.24	-	15.62	15.38	-	17.5